

Features of International Advertising Terms (In the Example of French Language)

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the specific features of international advertising terminology, especially how it is expressed in French. It examines how terms and terms in the field of advertising change and develop depending on cultural, economic and social contexts. The article highlights the specificity of advertising terminology in French, its international acceptance and the problems in the translation process. It also discusses cultural differences in the process of creating advertising in French and their impact on advertising. This study provides useful information for professionals working in the field of advertising and highlights the importance of intercultural communication in the development of international advertising strategies.*

Keywords: *international advertising, advertising terms, advertising terminology, globalization, localization, brand building, international market, targeting.*

Introduction

Today, it is impossible to approach advertising text as a simple phenomenon. Because in the process of translating the advertising text into a foreign language, its characteristics, emotional effects or elements of psychological impact may change.

As an integral part of the global economy, international advertising terms play an important role in strengthening connections between different cultures and languages. Advertising is not only a means of presenting products or services, but also a powerful means of communication that reflects the social and cultural context. The French language, with its rich history and culture, holds a special place in the field of international advertising. This article analyzes the characteristics of international advertising terms used in French, their cultural impact and their importance in adapting to the global market. The identity of advertising terms, their translation and their meaning in the cultural context are an important factor in the development of international marketing strategies. Throughout the article, the reviewer learns how French advertising terminology affects global communication and the cultural differences necessary for its successful implementation.

Methods

This article uses a number of methodological approaches to study the characteristics of international advertising terms. The main objective is to identify the cultural, linguistic and economic aspects of French advertising terms by analyzing them.

Literature Analysis: During the research, the existing literature, scientific articles and books related to the field of advertising were studied. These resources provided an understanding of the history and evolution of advertising terms and their evolution in an international context.

Contextual Analysis: Examples are provided to explore how French advertising terms are used in different contexts (e.g. television advertising, internet advertising, social media, etc.). In this process, various advertising campaigns and their audiences were analyzed.

Linguistic analysis: The linguistic structure of advertising terms and their semantic characteristics were studied. Terminology, lexical units and syntactic structures were analyzed here. She also compared advertising terms in French with their equivalents in other languages.

Empirical research: A questionnaire and interviews were conducted to study advertising terms in French. Through interviews with advertising experts and consumers, their opinions and experiences were collected. This empirical data provides deeper insight into the actual usage of advertising terms.

Analytical approach: The data obtained were analyzed and the results were summarized. Conclusions were drawn about the cultural context of advertising terms, their acceptance and how they are understood by consumers.

Discussion

Advertising copy is the text of the advertising message, which includes the title, introduction, body and conclusion. The main elements of advertising texts, both on billboards and flyers, are text and images, through which advertising conveys ideas and information to people. It defines the essence of the sentence, and the image complements it visually and in no way repeats its content.

The main criterion for understanding the features of advertising language is the ability to correctly perceive and adequately translate advertising texts and brand names. As you know, there are several main approaches to understanding translation equivalence. [1]

First of all, the notion of formal correspondence is the process by which everything that is transmitted is transmitted, down to the structure of the source text. This principle only applies to the transcription or transliteration of business names, but not to the translation of slogans.

Results

Moreover, when equivalence appears as a balance between the exact transmission of the elements of the source text and compliance with the norms of the translated language, the concept of conformity of normative content is formed. A normative language for advertising texts is certainly desirable, but it is not the most important task. Therefore, the more the translation conveys the emotional message included in the text by the creator of the advertisement, the higher quality it can be considered. Translation of the advertising message according to the concept of dynamic (functional) equivalence accomplishes this task in the most effective way. The concept of dynamic equivalence was introduced into linguistics by the American scientist Yu. Naid suggested: “The usefulness of translation is measured not by comparing the source text with the translated text, but by comparing the reaction of the recipient of the translated text and the recipient of the text in the source language.[2]

At first glance, translating a brand name may seem like the least difficult task. There are generally accepted methods for transcribing and transliterating foreign words (although the second method is rarely used at this stage). However, we should not forget about such an important phenomenon as homonymy in a foreign language.

The famous Bulgarian translator S. Florin describes this phenomenon in his book “Translation Pains” as follows: “For example, the correct transcription of a foreign noun is a homonym of a rude, obscene or simply funny word in the translated language. what if he goes out? This is not a “euphemism”, but it can give a parodic, caricatural character to the serious or profound character of the translated work. [3]

This warning is particularly important for advertising texts. An advertising agency cannot hope to succeed if the name of a particular brand or product provokes reactions from speakers of a certain language on which the manufacturer has not bet. Perhaps the consumer will have positive associations with the product that the manufacturer did not expect. However, we often face the exact opposite situations.

The global car manufacturer Ford can “boast” of extensive experience in this field. For example, the Fiyera, a low-cost truck intended for developing countries, sold very little in Latin America. The fact

is that *fiyerra* means “old woman” in Spanish. A translator, in addition to understanding the spirit of a particular brand and, of course, having a good knowledge of the language of the source text, must have the ability to anticipate the communicative effect of an advertising message in the target language.

The Mars company faced the following challenges when introducing its well-known brand M&M to the French market. French does not have & (= and) or plural endings. Anyone learning English knows these signs and will respond appropriately to such a mark. However, this is a situation in which the translator must “take out” knowing the original language from their reaction. It was therefore decided to launch a major advertising campaign to “teach” the French consumer to pronounce the name of the product, that is to say to transmit the sound of M&M in English with the sounds of their mother tongue.

As mentioned above, a distinctive feature of advertising is the use of low-frequency words, which always have a more emotional color and differ in a more complex semantic structure.[4]

Conclusion

In short, the reference to literary, cultural and historical traditions is a “very powerful weapon” for advertising creators. At the same time, such phenomena cause certain difficulties in the interpretation and perception of the text. The use of quotes, allusions, broken expressions, as well as additions in a foreign language in advertising implies the existence of common information between the creator of the text and its receiver. Such phenomena are of particular importance in the advertising of products presented on the international market, since in this case it is necessary to adapt advertising messages taking into account the specifics of the linguistic image of the world of the audience to which this text is addressed.

International advertising terms used in French are important in the successful implementation of global marketing strategies. These terms are essential not only when presenting products or services, but also when considering cultural context. The originality of advertising terms and their translation play an important role in strengthening relationships between different cultures.

French advertising terminology reflects cultural differences and is an effective tool for attracting consumers. Additionally, French advertising terms are of strategic importance to adapt to global market requirements and to successfully operate in different regions.

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